

Diversity **E**quity **I**nclusion

Managing Diversity in Smaller European Businesses: SME Perspective

2024-2025

Contributions

While the report is written by several colleagues, the survey has been developed, reviewed, tested and data collected by collective work of many within the DEI4SME project team. We briefly mention key contributions of all colleagues who were involved in implementing WP2, Activity 1 (Survey on DEI challenges for the under-represented groups), Activity 2 (Survey on DEI challenges for the SMEs), and Activity 5 (Report on DEI management in SME context framework).

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Definitions of the Main Concepts Used in the Surveys and this Report

Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is a conceptual framework that promotes the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially populations that have historically been underrepresented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

- **Diversity** refers to the representation or composition of various social identity groups in a work group, organization, or community.

- **Equity** involves providing resources according to the need to help diverse populations achieve their highest state of health and other functioning.

- **Inclusion** strives for an environment that offers affirmation, celebration, and appreciation of different approaches, styles, perspectives, and experiences.

Diversity & Identifications Explored:

Gender identity refers to one's deeply felt sense of being male, female, both, neither, or anywhere along the gender spectrum.

Belonging to the LGBTQIA+ community refers to an individual's lasting pattern of emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to individuals of the same gender, different genders, or multiple genders.

Age refers to the length of time that an individual has lived or existed since birth.

Language refers to systems of communication used by humans to convey meaning through a combination of sounds, symbols, and gestures. An individual's native language refers to the language learned from birth. **Accent** refers to the distinct patterns of pronunciation, intonations, and speech characteristics associated with speakers or a particular language or dialect.

Caregiving refers to the provision of assistance, support, and care to individuals who are unable to fully care for themselves due to age, illness, disability, or other circumstances.

Education here refers to different types and contexts. Formal education: primary education, secondary education, higher education. Vocational education: vocational training programs, apprenticeship.

Religion refers to a system of beliefs, practices, rituals, and moral values centred around the worship of a divine or supernatural being.

Students or those with little previous work experience refers to one's current educational path (student) or one's who recently graduated and/or one's feeling that their work experience is minimal.

Ethnic background refers to one's affiliation with a group based on shared social, cultural (e.g. language, religion, food, or heritage), and historical experiences derived from a common national or regional background. Ethnic groups are distinguished by their specific beliefs, values, behaviors, and sense of belonging. Individuals may identify with multiple ethnicities.

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1 Managing Diversity in Smaller European Businesses: SME Perspective

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Executive summary

The Key Insights and Implications from the Survey for SMEs

This report looks at how SMEs from Austria, Finland, Germany and Lithuania handle diversity, equity and inclusion. Most firms report adhering to legal requirements, but DEI management is still maturing, and most companies place themselves in the early “compliant” or “aware” tiers, while only a few claim advanced expertise. Few have appointed a named DEI person to lead the way and steer the company. Formal policies are uneven, reviews are sporadic and mentorship for under-represented staff is not for certain, and many firms don’t collect DEI data or monitor it. DEI software adoption is considered by a sizable proportion, yet actual adoption and usage remains unused. Benefits as reported by owner’s centre on better morale or occasional surges in creativity, but many struggle to see a concrete return. Overall, intent is widespread but execution lags, pointing to a need for practical resources and sustained support.

1.1 Methodology

This statistical survey analysis provides an overview of DEI (Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion) management practices in companies across the DEI4SME project partner countries: Austria, Finland, Germany, and Lithuania. The survey aimed to explore how SMEs perceive and address DEI issues in their daily operations.

The questionnaire consisted of four thematic sections: (1) basic company information, (2) human resource management, (3) DEI in strategic management, and (4) best practices. Each section included key definitions and explanations where necessary, ensuring clarity for respondents (e.g., definitions of diversity, equity, and inclusion were provided at the beginning of relevant sections).

Given the sensitivity of the topic, the questionnaire was designed to be as inclusive and neutral as possible, ensuring anonymity for all respondents. Participation was entirely voluntary, as stated in the ethics statement, and respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time.

Survey was translated into the local languages of all target countries. When first designing the survey, the English language was used, and its structure was discussed among academic and corporate project partners. Then, when internal agreement on the first draft of the survey was made, the English version of the survey was translated to Finnish, Swedish (the two national languages of Finland), Lithuanian, and German (spoken officially in both Austria and Germany). When translating, native speakers worked in teams to ensure that at least two native speakers

check the translation and localize the meanings making them not only linguistically, but also culturally correct. There was extensive effort to coordinate between German speaking project partners, ensuring that German version of the survey suits both Austrian and German speakers. Once the translations were complete, the survey was further tested with external stakeholders, at least five in each country gathering their feedback on clarity and structure of the survey. Once the feedback was gathered from all countries and jointly discussed, minor adjustments were made in all language versions and if needed further translated following the same process once again.

The survey primarily employed a quantitative approach to assess DEI practices in SMEs. However, some open-ended questions were included to allow respondents to clarify their perspectives or share best practices.

The questionnaire was distributed digitally through project tools and professional networks within the partner consortium. While this sampling method may introduce potential biases, it aligns with the project's objective of understanding DEI issues specifically within SMEs rather than providing a comprehensive statistical analysis of broader societal trends. To mitigate individual bias, the questionnaire included two specific questions designed to gauge respondents' personal perceptions of DEI.

1.2 Demographics

The survey consisted of 53 questions (148 questions and sub-questions). It was conducted during May and September 2024 with 137 full responses collected. The survey was conducted in Austria, Finland, Germany, and Lithuania (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of the company's head office

In Figure 1 respondents were asked to identify the country of where their represented organisation is located. Thirty respondents (21,9%) indicated Austria as the primary location of activities (head

office), 31 (22,6%) indicated Germany, 31 (22,6%) indicated Finland, and 38 (27,7%) indicated Lithuania. Seven (5,1%) respondents represent companies with head office located in Sweden, Norway, Estonia, or US.

Majority of the companies that respondents represent are of small size, having 10-49 employees (44 companies, 32,1%). As the survey and the project overall tackles SME issues, Figure 2 shows that 90,5% of the companies are below 250 employees.

Figure 2. Company size

Additionally, majority of the companies are operating under 2 million € annual turnover (54, 39,4%). Figure 3 presents the approximate annual turnover of the company for the previous fiscal year.

Figure 3. Annual turnover of respondents' companies' previous fiscal year

Respondents indicate that most of their represented companies operate for more than 20 years (69, 50,4%). Figure 4 indicates the distribution of companies by years operating.

Figure 4. Companies' years in operation

The sample organisations represent variety of industries. Figure 5 shows the main 6 industries under which respondents operate. Retail trade is most common in the sample (9, 6,6%). Education and human health activities are the next two main industries, represented by 8 companies each (5,8% each).

Figure 5. Top 6 industries of sample companies

Furthermore, it was interesting to see the scope of international activities of our sample companies. Figure 6 indicates that approximately a third of the respondents do not have any international operations (44, 32,1%). However, the remaining sample respondents state that they have at least minimal international activities (21, 15,3%), some (44, 32,1%) or extensive operations abroad (22, 16,1%) or is a unit of a foreign company (6, 4,4%).

Figure 6. Scope of the companies' international activities

1.3 Maturity of DEI management

With the survey we were able to grasp were in the DEI maturity scale stand the sample organisations. The data depicted in Figure 7 shows direct evaluation of DEI maturity of sample organisations by themselves. Looking at the whole sample, 5,8% of sample organisations attribute themselves to the level of **DEI experts**, being legally compliant, having implemented company's policies and processes for handling DEI, being proactive advocates of DEI inside and outside the company. Furthermore, companies **advanced in DEI** (8,8%) have legal compliance, enacted company's policies and processes for handling DEI. There are companies already **developing their DEI management** (17,5%), having legal compliance, currently developing company's policies and processes for handling DEI. **DEI aware** (27,7%) organisations indicate their legal compliance and current discussions on the need for further DEI actions. Most of the sample companies attribute themselves to **DEI compliant** (28,5%), having legal compliance, but taking no further actions in DEI management. Still, 11,7% of the sample companies state that they **lack DEI awareness**: they are not sure about their legal compliance or DEI actions. These results indicate clearly that there is space for improvement in managing DEI related issues.

Figure 7. DEI maturity rank by sample organisations

Majority of Austrian (33,3%) and Lithuanian sample organisations (39,5%) indicate that they are currently DEI compliant, meaning that they know the legal regulations and comply to them, but not necessarily move further to set the best practices in business in relation to DEI management. Respondents from German companies indicated that they are DEI aware (41,9%), meaning that these companies not only know the legal requirements, but discuss these issues in the company for the further steps. Finland is showing most cases of sample companies developing DEI management (22,6%), additionally being DEI aware (25,8%).

The following graphs support the statistics provided in Figure 7. One of the common practices could be to have a DEI appointed employee to represent these issues in the company. However, it is not mandatory in relation to EU regulations and in the sample countries as well. Only 12% of responding companies have DEI person appointed (0% of respondents say that they have appointed a DEI person in Austria, 19,4% in Germany, 3,2% in Finland, and 18,4% in Lithuania).

Figure 8-Figure 12 represent how organisations handle specifics of DEI management in recruitment process, monitoring inclusion, career advancement, training, and handling harassment. Out of the survey sample, in most cases (69%), Germany has policies and/or processes for handling the aforementioned areas, without concentrating on any specific diversity group. Whereas Austria (48,7%), Finland (46,5%), and Lithuania (39,5%) has the most common DEI issue management style of handling them on case-by-case bases.

Figure 8. Managing DEI issues in recruitment process

Figure 9. Monitoring inclusion

Figure 10. Managing DEI issues in career advancement

Figure 11. Managing DEI issues in training

Figure 12. Handling harassment

The results in figures Figure 8-Figure 12 are somewhat contradictory compared to results in figure 7, and in need of a more thorough investigation. Figure 7 shows that Germany is mostly DEI aware, meaning that they know the legal requirements to move further ahead. This is supported with the results of management practices shown above, where German sample companies indicate that they have policies/processes to manage DEI issues. However, even when there are more companies ranking themselves above DEI aware, it is not necessary that they have the supporting practices in place.

Considering the maturity of DEI management in companies, it is important to understand whether these practices are periodically reviewed and renewed according to the changes in the context. On average, 16,8% of sample organisations revise their existing priorities, processes, policies and ways of working to address the most critical issues related to DEI frequently; 53,3% review them occasionally; and 29,9% do not revise them. German sample companies are the ones to mostly

revise their DEI issue management (83,9%), whereas Lithuanian sample companies are the least likely to revise them (55,2%).

Additionally to the DEI maturity evaluation, sample companies were asked to prioritize DEI issue management. Figure 13 shows sample the DEI priority rank of sample companies. Austrian sample companies indicate that DEI initiatives are not a priority (40,0%) in their organisation or that they rank alongside other business priorities (26,7%). Clear majority of German sample companies state that DEI initiatives are not a priority (51,6%). Most of Finnish sample companies state that business priorities are more important than DEI initiatives (41,9%). Lithuanian sample companies indicate that they either have DEI initiatives alongside other business priorities (31,6%), or that DEI initiatives are not a priority (31,6%).

Figure 13. DEI initiative priority rank

In support to DEI priority rank, we have asked several questions of how the company sees DEI as an integral part of their organisation. Out of the sample companies, 65,6% feel that diverse perspectives are encouraged and valued in strategic-decision making and 66,6% feel that diverse perspectives are encouraged and valued in daily-decision making (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Diverse perspectives in strategic and daily decision making

Moreover, 51,4% of respondents notice that workforce diversity and inclusion help developing their business (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Workforce diversity and inclusion help develop business

Even though diverse perspectives are appreciated and seen beneficial in more than half of the sample companies, only 30,3% of them indicate that DEI is a part of the companies' identity (Figure 16).

Figure 16. DEI being a part of the company's identity

There is an uneven distribution among sample countries in whether they clearly understand the challenges (Figure 17) and the benefits (Figure 18) that DEI has to their business. Overall, challenges (47,1%) that are brought by DEI issues are slightly clearer to the sample organisations than the benefits (42,7%) addressing them could bring.

Figure 17. Understanding DEI challenges to business

Figure 18. Understanding DEI benefits to business

Followingly, 59,8% of sample companies would like to understand better how DEI can support their business (Figure 19). However, 74,4% of the respondents do not have sufficient resources to support DEI initiatives at work (Figure 20).

Figure 19. Need to increase understanding of how DEI can support business

Figure 20. Access to resources to support DEI initiatives at work

Figure 21 presents whether all sample organisations see any benefits of managing DEI issues in their company. Most commonly, companies find that employee job satisfaction has increased (22,6% of sample companies see this benefit) and that they have higher levels of innovation and creativity at work (19,7%). Finnish respondents were the ones to spot the most benefits of DEI issue management for their companies, as Austrian sample the least. However, it is visible that the benefits of managing DEI issues are yet still unclear for the 39,4% of respondents.

Figure 21. Benefits of DEI management

Overall, DEI issues in the sample companies are addressed mostly because of the laws demanding it. Evidently, only on some occasions the sample companies were able to see benefits of tackling these issues. Otherwise, more information is needed on how to engage with DEI in company level.

1.4 DEI in practice

Even though the sample companies are on their journey towards DEI management maturity, it is worthwhile to address what practices are being implemented. The survey included several questions about various practices that companies can engage when handling DEI issues. The following graph (fig. 22) addresses sample organisations' awareness, processes, and support structures for effective DEI management. They capture the extent to which employees understand reporting mechanisms, the presence of support programs for underrepresented groups, and the clarity of DEI success criteria. Additionally, they evaluate the organisation's ability to collect and monitor relevant DEI data in compliance with the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and ensure responsiveness to DEI-related requests.

Figure 22 indicates and supports previous chapter notions, that sample companies don't yet understand how to handle DEI issues, what data to collect and monitor. Moreover, mentorship is a rare practice to support the employees of underrepresented groups. However, more than 35% of all countries representatives state that they have a clear understanding of what it means to be successful in managing diversity, equity, and inclusion at work. Simultaneously, this being a mandatory practice demanded by laws in European countries, above 60% of sample organisations state that employees are familiarised with how to report any acts of exclusion, discrimination, or harassment happening at work.

Figure 22. General DEI management practices

With the survey it was also addressed, whether companies assure equity. In Figure 23 it is visible that sample companies try to ensure equity in their communities, but not all of them engage with these practices.

Figure 23. Equity assurance

In managing equity practices, we can see that some initiatives are more popular than others (Figure 24). Seventy-nine out of 137 sample companies provide resources and support in daily work according to individual or specific group's needs; 71 provide benefits to cater different needs (i.e. childcare, flexible work hours); and 62 provide resources for career development according to individual or specific group's needs. However, quotas and blind resume reviews are rarely adapted practices. Moreover, 21 sample organisations do not manage equity at work whatsoever.

Figure 24. Equity management, count

The survey also addressed DEI management practices that are related to external factors or extended stakeholders, as indicated in Figure 25. These indicators assess an organisation's commitment to measuring, reporting, and actively fostering DEI. They reflect efforts to track DEI progress through data collection and key performance measures, ensure transparency by sharing DEI reports with value chain partners, and encourage management involvement in building an inclusive workplace. Additionally, they highlight engagement with value chain workers, the use of collective bargaining agreements, and the alignment of DEI initiatives with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Most commonly by the sample companies, the management actively participates in creating an inclusive climate at work (81 individual cases). Collective bargaining (58) and engaging with value chain workers (52) are also visible practice, though not that common. However, it is rare that sample companies request their partners in value or supply chain to prepare reporting information on their DEI activities; design initiatives or processes for DEI with the aim to also support the achievement of one or more of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals; or implement measures (such as Key Performance Indicators) to ensure the effectiveness of equal opportunities, diversity, or inclusion policies at work.

Figure 25. DEI practices

Even though not all practices that could be applicable in managing DEI are implemented by the sample organisations, it is clear that they are taking steps to assure safe environment for their employees of various diversity groups (Figure 26). Supposedly, this can be done by involving the employees in the company's decision-making process frequently (30,7%) or at least occasionally (62,8%).

Figure 26. Safe space for employees

Additional practice that is important in the project of DEI4SME is the use of digital tools to support DEI management. However, none of the sample company uses software for planning, implementing, and monitoring diversity, equity, and inclusion-related issues, though 25,6% of them would like to have such a tool in their company. Similarly, 28,5% of sample companies would like to have a software to report compliance with various laws and guidelines such as CSRD.

1.5 Inclusion of people of different diversity groups

Seeing, that companies do apply some practices and in general have a care for different needs of their employees and other stakeholders, the survey invited the respondents to address whether there are different diversity dimensions represented among their employees and managers. The following graph (Figure 27) depicts the answers to the statement “To my knowledge, in our company we have these diversity dimensions represented among employees”. In most cases, company representatives know that there are employees working in the organisation of various age, speaking various languages or dialects, who are caregivers, and have various educational backgrounds. On the other hand, employees with various disabilities or those who identify themselves with the LGBTQIA+ community are not recognized or are not included in the workforce of the sample companies.

Figure 27. Employees representing different diversity dimensions

Interestingly, employees of the least represented diversity groups are the ones whom the representatives of the company were least able to identify. Therefore, in Figure 28 the answer of “I don’t know” whether this diversity group is represented among employees is visualised.

Figure 28. Uncertainty in employee diversity representation

Among management teams, it can be postulated that there are even more inequalities among different diversity group representation (Figure 29). Evidently, there are people of different age and educational background covering managerial functions among the sample companies. However, it is rare that people of various ethnicities, few work experience (students), disabilities, LGBTQIA+ diversities are represented among the management. Sadly, gender representation only reaches 40%.

Figure 29. Managers representing different diversity dimensions

A very similar situation can be spectated in the management as in the employee representation when it comes to whether the managers know if different diversity dimensions are represented (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Uncertainty in management diversity representation

In conclusion, the sample organisations are yet covering their path towards more inclusive, diverse, and equitable management of their employee communities. Some practices, that are attributed to DEI issue management, are already in place. However, seldomly sample organisations can cover all the expenses that these additional processes require. This results in unequal inclusion of various diversity dimensions in to the working environment.

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